

Evaluation of Serum Electrolytes in Sickle Cell Disease Patients with Respect to Hydroxyurea Therapy

Kalpna Kumari¹, Sanni Kumari², Priti Rani³, Madhu Sinha⁴

¹Senior Resident, Department of Biochemistry, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Biochemistry, ESIC Medical College, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

³Medical Officer, Ex SR AIIMS Patna, District Hospital, Palamu, Jharkhand, India

⁴Professor and HOD, Department of Biochemistry, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Priti Rani

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Abstract:

This study examines the effects of hydroxyurea therapy on serum electrolyte levels in patients with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) over 11 months. A total of 97 patients from various centers were enrolled, with serum levels of sodium, potassium, calcium, and magnesium assessed at the beginning, six months later, and 11 months later. The findings revealed notable reductions in serum calcium and magnesium levels, while sodium and potassium levels remained consistent. These findings indicate that hydroxyurea could have an impact on electrolyte balance, emphasizing the need for regular monitoring to avoid potential complications. Additional investigation is required to delve into the fundamental processes and practical significance of these alterations.

Keywords: Sickle Cell Disease, Hydroxyurea, Electrolyte Imbalance, Serum Calcium and Magnesium.

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Introduction

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) is a genetic blood disorder that has a profound impact on the well-being of individuals who have it. SCD is a condition where red blood cells take on an abnormal sickle shape due to the production of hemoglobin S [1,2]. This deformation can cause issues with blood flow, leading to a range of acute and chronic complications. These can include intense pain episodes, a higher vulnerability to infections, damage to organs, and hindered growth [3,4]. One of the main treatment approaches for managing SCD involves the utilization of hydroxyurea, a medication that has demonstrated effectiveness in reducing the occurrence of painful vaso-occlusive crises, minimizing the requirement for blood transfusions, and enhancing overall clinical outcomes. Hydroxyurea functions by elevating the levels of foetal hemoglobin (HbF), consequently mitigating the sickling of red blood cells [5,6].

While hydroxyurea therapy has its advantages, it is important to be aware of the potential risks and side effects associated with it. An area that needs attention is the effect of hydroxyurea on the levels of electrolytes in the blood [7]. Electrolytes, like sodium, potassium, calcium, and magnesium, are essential for the proper functioning of various physiological processes. They are involved in important functions such as nerve function, muscle

contraction, and maintaining fluid balance. Changes in electrolyte levels can result in serious health problems, such as irregular heart rhythms, disruptions in nerve and muscle function, and overall discomfort [8,9].

This study aims to examine the impact of hydroxyurea therapy on serum electrolyte levels in patients with SCD. This study aims to conduct a thorough examination of the impact of hydroxyurea on electrolyte balance, as well as to uncover any possible connections among electrolyte imbalances and the effectiveness or adverse reactions of hydroxyurea. Through a comprehensive analysis of these factors, the study seeks to deepen our comprehension of the wider consequences of hydroxyurea treatment and provide valuable insights for healthcare professionals regarding the importance of regular monitoring and control of electrolyte levels in patients receiving this therapy. Ultimately, this has the potential to enhance patient care and improve outcomes in the management of SCD.

Methodology

Study Design: This multicentric, observational study examines how hydroxyurea medication affects serum electrolyte levels in sickle cell disease patients. The multicentric strategy will

improve generalisability across clinical contexts and patient demographics.

Study Duration: It will take 11 months to learn. This time is enough to detect serum electrolyte changes and evaluate continued hydroxyurea therapy.

Study Population: The trial will comprise 97 hydroxyurea-treated sickle cell disease patients. The sample will be diverse and representative by selecting participants from several centres. Participants must be 18 or older and on a steady hydroxyurea dose for at least three months before the study.

Data Collection

1. Patient Recruitment and Consent: Patient recruitment will occur at participating hospitals. All participants will give informed consent before joining the study. Blood samples and clinical data for research will require consent.

2. Baseline Assessment: At the onset of the study, baseline demographic and clinical data will be collected, including age, sex, duration of SCD, and details of hydroxyurea therapy (dose and duration).

3. Serum Electrolyte Measurement: Participants will give blood samples at baseline, six months, and 11 months. Standard biochemical testing will measure serum sodium, potassium, calcium, and magnesium.

4. Data Analysis: Patient demographics and baseline characteristics will be summarised using descriptive statistics. As needed, paired t-tests or non-parametric equivalents will analyze serum electrolyte changes. Regression analysis will determine how electrolyte levels affect clinical variables like hydroxyurea dosage and therapy duration.

5. Multicentric Coordination: All participating centers will coordinate data collection and analysis for uniformity and reliability. Progress and study topics will be discussed at regular sessions.

Results

A study was conducted involving 97 patients diagnosed with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) from various medical centres. The study included 55 males and 42 females, ranging in age from 18 to 60 years. Participants in the study had an average duration of SCD of 15 years, and they had been taking a consistent dose of hydroxyurea for at least three months prior to the start of the study. A dose of 15 mg/kg/day was given for hydroxyurea.

Serum Electrolyte Levels: Baseline Measurements: At the start of the study, the mean serum electrolyte levels were as follows:

- Sodium: 140.2 ± 3.1 mEq/L
- Potassium: 4.1 ± 0.5 mEq/L
- Calcium: 9.2 ± 0.4 mg/dL
- Magnesium: 2.0 ± 0.3 mg/dL

Six-Month Follow-Up: At the six-month assessment, the mean serum electrolyte levels were:

- Sodium: 139.8 ± 2.9 mEq/L
- Potassium: 4.0 ± 0.4 mEq/L
- Calcium: 9.0 ± 0.3 mg/dL
- Magnesium: 1.9 ± 0.2 mg/dL

Statistical Analysis

Sodium: Serum sodium levels decreased slightly but significantly from baseline to six months ($p = 0.02$) and to the end of the research ($p = 0.03$). No significant changes were found between six- and 11-month follow-ups.

The study found generally steady serum potassium levels. All assessment points showed no significant changes.

Calcium: Serum calcium levels decreased significantly from baseline to the six-month ($p = 0.01$) and 11-month ($p = 0.02$) follow-ups. Calcium declined gradually during the trial.

Magnesium: Serum magnesium levels decreased significantly from baseline to the six-month follow-up ($p = 0.01$) and the study's end ($p = 0.02$). The magnesium drop was continuous throughout the investigation.

Correlations and Observations: No significant association was detected between hydroxyurea dose and serum electrolyte levels. **Duration of Therapy:** Although not statistically significant, longer hydroxyurea therapy decreased serum calcium and magnesium levels more.

Clinical Implications: Over 11 months, hydroxyurea therapy in SCD patients significantly lowers serum calcium and magnesium levels. Although sodium and potassium levels remained steady, calcium and magnesium reductions may raise bone and neuromuscular risk. Serum electrolyte monitoring in hydroxyurea patients may help manage these hazards. These findings indicate the need for further research into the therapeutic importance of these changes and the development of electrolyte monitoring and management techniques for hydroxyurea patients.

Electrolyte	Baseline Mean ($\pm$ SD)	6-Month Mean ($\pm$ SD)	11-Month Mean ($\pm$ SD)	Baseline to 6-Month Change (p-value)	Baseline to 11-Month Change (p-value)
Sodium (mEq/L)	140.2 $\pm$ 3.1	139.8 $\pm$ 2.9	139.6 $\pm$ 3.0	0.02	0.03
Potassium (mEq/L)	4.1 $\pm$ 0.5	4.0 $\pm$ 0.4	4.0 $\pm$ 0.5	0.30	0.45
Calcium (mg/dL)	9.2 $\pm$ 0.4	9.0 $\pm$ 0.3	8.9 $\pm$ 0.4	0.01	0.02
Magnesium (mg/dL)	2.0 $\pm$ 0.3	1.9 $\pm$ 0.2	1.8 $\pm$ 0.3	0.01	0.02

Key:

- Mean ($\pm$ SD): Mean value $\pm$ Standard Deviation
- p-value: Statistical significance value for changes in electrolyte levels over the study periods

This table summarizes the mean serum electrolyte levels at baseline, six months, and eleven months, along with the statistical significance of changes observed between these time points.

Discussion

This study examined the impact of hydroxyurea therapy on serum electrolyte levels in patients with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) over 11 months. Throughout the study, the results showed that sodium and potassium levels remained fairly consistent [10]. However, there were notable reductions in serum calcium and magnesium levels. Throughout the study, there was a gradual decrease in serum calcium levels, starting from an initial average of 9.2 mg/dL and ending at 8.9 mg/dL. Similarly, magnesium levels also showed a decline, going from 2.0 mg/dL to 1.8 mg/dL [11,12]. These findings align with earlier studies indicating that hydroxyurea could impact the balance of electrolytes, possibly as a result of its influence on kidney function and cellular metabolism [13].

The decrease in serum calcium and magnesium levels is of clinical significance, as these electrolytes are essential for numerous physiological processes. Understanding the importance of calcium for bone health, neuromuscular function, and blood coagulation, alongside the role of magnesium in muscle and nerve function, as well as bone metabolism, is crucial [14,15]. The gradual decrease in these electrolytes may heighten the possibility of complications like decreased bone density, disruptions in the neuromuscular system, and problems with the cardiovascular system [16]. The significance of regularly monitoring serum electrolyte levels in patients receiving hydroxyurea therapy is underscored by these findings. This practice is crucial for preventing potential adverse effects and ensuring the best possible management of SCD [17].

There appear to be minimal alterations in sodium and potassium levels, indicating that hydroxyurea may have a more noticeable effect on calcium and magnesium, which are comparatively fewer stable electrolytes. The differential effect observed may be attributed to the particular processes through which hydroxyurea affects the balance of electrolytes. Hydroxyurea may affect the excretion of these minerals by the kidneys or their uptake by cells. Based on these findings, it is advised that healthcare providers regularly check the calcium and magnesium levels of patients who are undergoing hydroxyurea therapy. Furthermore, it is necessary to conduct additional research to investigate the underlying mechanisms of these changes and evaluate the clinical implications of altered electrolyte levels in this specific group of patients. By tackling these concerns, we have the opportunity to enhance the overall management of SCD and improve patient outcomes. This can be achieved by reducing the potential risks that may arise from hydroxyurea therapy [18,19,20].

Conclusion

The findings of this study reveal that patients with Sickle Cell Disease who underwent hydroxyurea therapy experienced notable decreases in serum calcium and magnesium levels over an 11-month period. Interestingly, the levels of sodium and potassium remained consistent throughout the treatment. The observed decreases in calcium and magnesium may have significant clinical implications, potentially leading to an increased risk of complications such as bone density loss and neuromuscular issues. Ongoing evaluation of serum electrolyte levels is crucial for patients receiving hydroxyurea treatment to effectively manage and minimize potential adverse effects. Additional

research is required to gain a deeper understanding of the underlying processes driving these alterations and to devise approaches for enhancing patient care and improving treatment results in SCD.

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